

A REVIEW OF THEORETICAL VIEWS ON GREETINGS AND WISHES

Ernazarova Nargiza Xidirovna

UzSWLU, senior teacher

e-mail: nargizaernazarova1111@gmail.com

Abstract: This article explores the intricate nature of speech culture, particularly focusing on the phenomena of "congratulations" and "wishes" as vital components of communication that reflect national characteristics and collective mentality. It highlights the contributions of various linguists who have examined the strategies, semantic structures, and cultural significance of these speech acts across different societies. The research reveals that "congratulations" and "wishes" serve as essential speech etiquette units that convey positive sentiments, regulate social behavior, and adhere to societal norms.

Key words: speech etiquette, congratulation, wish, speaker, addressee, communication, genre.

The speech culture of a community is a complex, varied, and historically evolving phenomenon. The elements of speech etiquette represent distinct cultural and historical values, serving as crucial means of regulating behavior, which are essential for both individuals and societies.

"Congratulations" and "wishes" function as socio-cultural phenomena that reflect national characteristics and collective mentality. What sets them apart from other concepts is their extensive communicative expression within speech acts.

A number of research works have been carried out in the field of speech act of congratulations and wishes by linguists in the world. Among them, Muhammad Mahzari, Humeira John, Kimia Avazpour, Qin Panpan, Zhang Hao, N.M. Mekeko, D.F. Komorova, T.P. Sukhoterina, E.V. Vdovina, N.V. Nemchinova, D. Nizeeva,

L.A. Khisamova, N.V. Dudkina, E.V. Zaitseva, T.V. Annushkina, M.S.Gonchar, K.A.Akenteva, S.V.Shatalova, E.B.Mandjjeva, G.A.Nishanova have discussed congratulation strategies, their semantic formulas, similar and different aspects of congratulations and wishes in the cultures of different nations, theoretical problems, national and cultural characteristics, description of congratilations and wishes as a genre, linguistic description, from the point of view of cognitive-discursive paradigm description, revealed and analyzed their problems as the speech genre model in their scientific works.

According to N.M. Mekeko, "wish" SEU (speech etiquette unit) is such a speech that informs the addressee of the speaker's statements about his wishes, usually hoping that they will come true; their use is strictly regulated by the rules of behavior accepted in a particular society. There are standard and individual wishes used in spoken and written forms. "Wishes" thematic group is inextricably linked with the "Congratulations" communicative situation. It is found that most of the SEU information is heard in the toasts given on various holidays. In addition, the SEU "Wish" thematic group: "Greeting", "Farewell", "Gratitude", "Advice", "Praise", "Request", "Appeal" is used in communicative situations and advertising texts where they play an important role. [1; 32]

D.F. Komorova believes that within the illocutionary force all wishes are divided into with etiquette and without etiquette. Etiquette-style positive wishes can be contrasted with negative wishes, including curses that have nothing to do with manners. Ethical and non-ethical wishes are distinguished by the unity of the two components they contain: the desires within the framework of decency are based on ritual + evaluation, and the desires that are not within the framework of decency are based on feelings + evaluation.

Wish, which is a speech act with etiquette, is a polite speech, an act performed by the speaker to show sympathy to the addressee and hope for his future well-being, thereby complying with the norms of etiquette accepted in a certain society.

The speaker who expresses the hope that the wish will come true in the future does not encourage the addressee to take any action and does not take responsibility for its implementation.

Non-etiquette speech of wishes is speech act and giving freedom to feelings, carried out in order to express hope for a certain situation in his future life, to inform about the speaker's assessment of the receiver's characteristics or actions, or about the situation. [2;10]

According to T. P. Sukhoterina, "Congratulations" as an event are some stereotypes of rituals, values, principles, and norms of behavior that imply strict adherence to the ritual and holiday culture, manners. "Congratulations" are used in semi-prepared, semi-formal, informal, and formal areas of communication. The "congratulations" hypergenre, like any phatic, has a certain symbolic meaning, describes attitude, recognition, non-recognition, status relations.

"Congratulations" is one of the forms of communication between native speakers, which reflects the culture, language style and speech culture of the author of "congratulations". As a phenomenon of folk culture, "congratulations" in the hypergenre of ritual and celebration are presented in a bright, colorful way. Authors use emotionally expressive, positive language tools. [3;37]

E. V. Vdovina believes that congratulations as a speech act is a polite speech act performed by the speaker to express sympathy and joy for a real event that is in the interests of the addressee. Wishes defines it as a polite speech act that is usually performed by the speaker in order to express attention and sympathy to the addressee and hope for prosperity in his future life, thus complying with the standards of etiquette accepted in this society. [4;113]

N.V. Nemchinova analyses that congratulation is an element of verbal communication, in which praise, compliment, expression of the interlocutor's qualities and services, his positive aspects, success, an important date in his life or his work and creative activity is noted, and congratulations are always a certain

event, date , is related to the event, so he believes that it should be timely and relevant in the first place. [5;10]

And N.V. Dudkina concludes that the genre of congratulatory speech includes: 1) the presence of the addresser (congratulator) and recipient (congratulated), and the latter is actually the object of the created text, because this text is the real and potential of a certain person or group represents the qualities. In this direction towards the addressee, as well as in the positive tone of the congratulatory text, the phatic beginning of the congratulatory genre is manifested;

2) the existence of a reason, that is, an event in the recipient's life that is evaluated as "joyful and pleasant". This event is the basis for creating a congratulating text, and at the same time determines its content. Often, this event plays an important role in the composition of congratulations, because the attitude towards the addressee is evaluated. [6;142]

According to T.V. Annushkina, a congratulatory speech is a speech created for a holiday or a solemn occasion, which includes praise, good wishes and greetings. Congratulatory speech is the simplest but very important type of speech for any society and human life. Congratulatory (celebratory, solemn) speech organizes the activity of any community, because on holidays people celebrate their success and talk about the important things in life, confirm the main ideological values and build the future with good intentions with predictions.

Accompanying congratulations compliments and congratulations are complementary and contrasting relationships. As a genre, congratulations can include not only praise, but also good wishes, a description of the addressee's successes, references to his past, etc. [7;9]

The main genres of K.A. Akenteva's holiday speech are "congratulations", "wishes" and "toast". "Congratulations" is aimed at creating or strengthening a special positive emotional and psychological state of the recipient. The author gives a collective, positive assessment of the holiday event, creates an ideal image of the

recipient in accordance with social norms. The content of the text is determined by the idea of the holiday and socio-cultural factors. [8;19]

According to Zhang Hao, the congratulatory speech act as a polite speech regulated by the rules of speech behavior and is an action performed by the receiver to express positive feelings caused by a happy, pleasant event related to the addressee (recipients). [9;15]

To conclude, congratulations as an event are some stereotypes of rituals, values, foundations, norms of behavior that imply strict adherence to the ritual and holiday culture, manners. "Congratulations" is one of the forms of communication between native speakers, which reflects the culture, language style and speech culture of the author of "congratulations".

Congratulation is an element of oral communication, in which praise, compliment, expression of the interlocutor's qualities and services, his positive aspects, success, an important date in his life or his work and creative activity are recorded.

Wishes are polite speech acts that are usually performed by the speaker in order to show attention and sympathy to the addressee and hope for prosperity in his future life, thus complying with the standards of etiquette accepted in this society. holiday and socio-cultural factors.

References

1.Мекеко Наталия Михайловна. Сопоставительный анализ функционирования единиц речевого этикета тематической группы «пожелание» в английском и русском языках. Диссертация на соискание учёной степени кандидата филологических наук, Москва – 2001.

2.Коморова Дарья Федоровна. Прагмалингвистические особенности пожелания в немецком и русском языках. Автореферат диссертации на соискание ученой степени кандидата филологических наук, Томск-2005.

3. Сухотерина Татьяна Павловна. «Поздравление» как гипержанр естественной письменной русской речи. Диссертация на соискание ученой степени кандидата филологических наук. Барнаул – 2007. С.34

4. Вдовина Екатерина Васильевна. Поздравление и пожелание в речевом этикете: концептуальный и коммуникативный анализ. Диссертация на соискание ученой степени кандидата филологических наук. Москва, 2007.

5. Немчинова Наталья Викторовна. Когнитивно-дискурсивное исследование текста корпоративной поздравительной открытки. Автореферат диссертации на соискание учёной степени кандидата филологических наук. Барнаул-2010

6. Дудкина Ника Валерьевна. Речевой жанр «поздравление» в русской и американской лингвокультурах Диссертация на соискание ученой степени кандидата филологических наук. Ростов-на-Дону – 2011.

7. Аннушкина Татьяна Владимировна. Поздравительная речь в разных сферах общения: содержание – композиция – стиль. Автореферат диссертации на соискание ученой степени кандидата филологических наук. Москва, 2016.

8. Акентьева Ксения Алексеевна. Миромоделирующая функция жанра «поздравление» в политическом и маркетинговом дискурсах. Автореферат диссертации на соискание ученой степени кандидата филологических наук. Томск – 2022.

9. Чжан Хао. Речевые акты «Поздравление» и «Пожелание» в русской речи. Автореферат диссертации на соискание ученой степени кандидата филологических наук. Москва – 2022.